

The Application of POAC Management in the Tourism Sector in Post-Pandemic Economic Recovery Based on E-Commerce

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Abstract:

This study analyzes the management carried out to carry out economic recovery in the tourism sector affected by the Covid-19 pandemic. From time to time, this pandemic continues to find solutions. So that the national and global economy can recover as before. Some countries have carried out various stages of economic recovery, and the fact is that the covid-19 pandemic is still affecting world events. The covid-19 virus first appeared in Wuhan, Hubei, China, in December 2019. As of October 2021, more than 238,662,395 cases have been reported worldwide. Of course, this has a huge impact on the world economy, especially harming the tourism industry. Because the pandemic has imposed social restrictions on the country, both inter-regional and international tourists. This study discusses the implementation of POAC management including 1.) Planning work to achieve economic recovery and national resilience; 2) organizational effects of economic recovery and national resilience; 3) drivers of economic and national resilience recovery; 4)

regulations impacting economic recovery and defense. Based on a review of a previous journal published.

Keywords: *management application, tourism sector, post-pandemic economic recovery, e-commerce.*

Introduction

Economic recovery is inactivity aimed to reduce the economic impact of Covid-19. In addition to overcoming the crisis in a healthy way, the government will certainly carry out economic recovery and resilience activities in response to the economic impact of reduced community activities, the state, especially the informal sector or SMEs. Affected by the outbreak, the economic situation in Indonesia and even the world is experiencing serious problems. Therefore, each country needs to take economic recovery measures for its own sustainable development. There are many ways that the

government has to restore the economy, one of which is to revive the economy by implementing new policies for tourism. Which sector has been severely affected by the Covid-19 virus pandemic? Of course, in addition to harming the private sector, the impact of Covid-19 on tourism has an impact on the country's income or foreign exchange. To that end, the government must act now to recover the economy as quickly as possible. This study examines the impact of planning, organizing, mobilizing, and controlling economic recovery, POAC Management Literature Review As an important study material, it is necessary to study Economic Recovery during the Covid-19

Pandemic Period. Based on this description, this article aims to determine the influence of POAC management on the tourism sector, the influence of POAC management on post-pandemic economic recovery, the influence of POAC management on e-commerce, the influence of the tourism sector on post-pandemic economic recovery, and the influence of the tourism sector on e-commerce.

Literature Review

POAC Management

Planning Economic Recovery. According to Hasibuan (2007), planning is a series of decisions presented as a guide to achieving the desired goals. The significance of planning according to Tjokroamidjojo (2011) as wide as possible is the activity of preparing something systematically, which is done to achieve your goals. Planning is one way to achieve economic recovery and national resilience, and of course well-structured planning or planning. Because the COVID-19 pandemic has had a tremendous impact on the economy over the past two years. so the program's economic recovery can be achieved according to the objectives, the role of stakeholders is needed and this application is well run by the community.

Furthermore, the purpose of planning is to define organizational goals and determine strategies, procedures, and budgets to produce appropriate outputs already established.

Organizing. Of course, in implementing the economic recovery plan, the government needs to improve the institutions participating in this program. Therefore, Indonesian President Joko Widodo A committee was formed to focus on economic containment and National recovery policies due to the Covid-19 pandemic. The commission was established by a presidential decree signed Meeting with President Joko Widodo on Monday, July 20, 2020. In addition to these tasks, the committee also, of course, handles layoffs in companies affected by the Covid-19 pandemic The same applies under the guidance of the relevant ministries (Norman et al., 2020).

Actuating. After the planning process has been carried out properly, the next step is to execute or implement all the plans that are ready. in the planning above, one of the efforts to recover the national economy is called eliminating the Luxury Goods Sales Tax (Dharma et al., 2019). The benefit of implementation is that it provides direction to employees and enables them to execute core tasks according to the skills possessed and available human quality resources (Irenius, 2014).

The Controlling. Economic recovery board is subordinate to the President and is accountable to the President. The committees referred to in Article 1 include: 1) the Policy Committee, 2) the Covid-19 Handling Task Force 3) the state-owned Economic Recovery and Transformation Task Force. (Norman et al., 2020) The policy committee is responsible for making strategic decisions The President also has the responsibility to accelerate pandemic recovery, economic recovery, and economic transformation.

The Chief Executive in part three, The task of paragraph (2) is to integrate and coordinate the implementation of the Strategic Policy for the Acceleration of Covid-19 Handling and Economic Recovery of the nation (Noman et al., 2020) The Covid-19 Handling Task Force has an obligation to solve these problems Also quickly and accurately in implementation related to handling Covid-19 and Supervise the implementation of strategic policies related to Covid-19.

Tourism Sector

The tourism department is one of the largest foreign exchange earners in Indonesia. The 2015-2019 National High School term development plan determines five program priorities The development of the next five years is infrastructure, maritime, energy, food, and tourism of the five sectors, tourism is designated as the leading sector.

Post-Pandemic Economic Recovery. Recovery planning according to Coppola is defined in Herdiana (2020) as "emergency management functions of countries, communities, families,

and individuals repairing, rebuilding or recovering what has been lost, Lost due to disasters". Disaster recovery is national, social, home, and personal improvement, rebuilding or rebuilding what has been lost to a disaster.

This is in line with this opinion. Haas, Kates, and Bowden (1977) state recovery is predictable and consists of identifiable parts that occur sequentially, choices and decisions are driven by value, with results emphasizing a return to normalcy or the latest combination of sustainability-related actions. From both perspectives, it can be concluded that post-disaster elections are an effort by governments, families, and individuals to recover what has been lost due to disasters and restore normalcy.

E-Commerce Based

Electronic commerce (e-commerce) is the process of buying, selling, or exchanging products, services, and information through computer networks (Utama, 2017). Electronic commerce is a part of e-commerce that is broader in scope, not only around business, but also working with business partners, customer service, job openings, and others.

According to Siregar (2010), e-commerce is not only a website network needed, but also database

technology, electronic mail/email, and other non-computer technical forms, such as freight forwarding systems and e-commerce payment methods (Utama, 2017). E-commerce is defined as the buying and selling of products, services, and information done electronically using computer networks. One of the networks used is the Internet. E-Commerce is part of the "E-Commerce" business that is done using electronic transmission (Hildamizanthi, 2011).

Implementing e-commerce requires attention to the value chain Infrastructure including distribution system infrastructure (flow of goods), payment infrastructure (flow of funds), and information system infrastructure (information flow). If all three are implemented correctly, e-commerce campaigns can run just right. Utama (2017) emphasizes the supply chain system from supplier to the factory, providing warehousing, distribution, and transportation services for end customers, which need to be integrated into Enterprise systems to build supply chain visibility.

Based on the study of theory and the results of previous research above, the following framework of thinking was obtained:

Figure 1. Framework Thinking

Materials and Methods

The method used in this study is the *systematic literature review (SLR) method*. Data was obtained from journals published in google scholar which totaled 20 journals reviewed. The *systematic literature review method* or commonly referred

to as the systematic literature review research method is one of the methods in research that identifies, assesses, and interprets problems that exist in a problem topic, as well as answers the research questions that have been explained (Ayu et al., 2021).

Results

Table 1. Previous Research Tables Related To

No	Authors	Research Results	The Similarities
1.	Farhan Saputra dan Hapzi Ali (2022)	POAC management has a positive influence because it can provide a reference in carrying out economic recovery during the pandemic.	POAC's management strategy has a positive influence because it can provide a reference for carrying out economic recovery during the pandemic.
2.	Ika Fitriani, Nining Sudiyarti, dan M. Nur Fietroh (2020)	POAC's management strategy has a positive influence on economic recovery, as it provides improvement and development of good business continuity.	POAC's management strategy has a positive influence and provides improvement and development of business continuity as an effort to recover the economy
3.	Margareta Evi, Ridwan Faizal Ramadhani, dan Risna Andrianto (2022)	POAC management has a positive influence on economic recovery because overcoming economic problems requires strategies to recover life from the pandemic.	POAC management has a positive influence on economic recovery because overcoming economic problems requires strategies to recover life from the pandemic.
4.	Modjo M (2020)	Leveling the way for post-pandemic economic strengthening	POAC management affects national economic recovery
5.	Sa'adah, Khairul Shaleh, Dini Arwaty, Fitri Sukmawati, R. Ferry Mulyawan, dan Daniel Nababan (2022)	The tourism sector is a contributor to Indonesia's national income, therefore, the tourism sector has a very important positive role	The tourism sector is a contributor to Indonesia's national income, therefore, the tourism sector has a very important positive role
6.	Ikang Murapi, Dewi Ayu Oki Astarini, dan Muliani (2022)	The tourism sector is a sector that has a positive influence because it is a large contributor to national income. The use of technology and information is one of the efforts to save the tourism sector in the post-pandemic.	The tourism sector is a sector that has a positive influence because it is a large contributor to national income.
7.	Wihardiyani (2021)	The tourism sector plays a very positive role in the economy by providing the largest contributor to national income. The implementation of the digitalization era plays a positive role in improving the tourism sector	The tourism sector plays a very positive role in the economy by providing the largest contributor to national income.
8.	Muhammad Iqbal Ansory, Yudhistira Harisandi, dan Raissa Zaerlina Balqis (2022)	The tourism sector plays a very positive role in the economy because most of the income of the Indonesian people comes from the tourism sector. The empowerment of	The tourism sector plays a very positive role in the economy because most of the income of the

No	Authors	Research Results	The Similarities
		MSMEs plays a positive role for the community as a support for the revival of the tourism sector	Indonesian people comes from the tourism sector
9.	Muhammad Saputra, Kurnia Fadila, Joko Triloka (2022)	POAC's management strategy has a positive effect on every activity so that the activities carried out run effectively and efficiently and E-Commerce has a positive effect on these activities	POAC's management strategy has a positive effect on every activity so that the activities carried out run effectively and efficiently and E-Commerce has a positive effect on these activities
10.	Kevin Satria Prajatama, Endang Larasati, Dyah Lituhayu (2022)	E-Commerce has a positive influence but the planning has not been fully controlled on the sustainability of an activity.	E-Commerce has a positive influence but the planning has not been fully controlled on the sustainability of an activity.
11.	Adiyah Hermawati, Choirul Anam, Survival (2021)	E-Commerce has a positive influence on the sustainability of activity using an organizational system	E-Commerce has a positive influence on the sustainability of activity using an organizational system
12.	Yani Sri Mulyani (2021)	The use of technology through electronics or e-commerce has a positive influence	The use of technology through electronics or e-commerce has a positive influence
13.	Juita L.D Bessie	E-commerce has an important influence on business activities in the tourism sector commonly referred to as e-tourism which is used for promotional activities and tourism transactions	E-commerce has an important influence on business activities in the tourism sector commonly referred to as e-tourism which is used for promotional activities and tourism transactions
14.	Riski Isminar Ardianti (2016)	The promotion of the tourism industry has a positive effect on increasing the number of tourist visitors	The promotion of the tourism industry has a positive effect on increasing the number of tourist visitors
15.	Ikhsan Fuady, Hadi Suprpto, Dwi Masrina (2020)	The development of technology (e-commerce) has a positive effect because it can revive the tourism industry in the future	The development of technology (e-commerce) has a positive effect because it can revive the tourism industry in the future
16.	Jusmiati & Muh. Arifi M. Salim (2017)	Governance and development of the tourism sector by implementing POAC management	Application of POAC management in the development and management of tourism objects
17.	Chandra Khoerunnisa, Maulana Rifai & Kariena Febriantini (2022)	POAC management as a foundation in achieving the goals of the soul temple tourist destination	Implementation of POAC management to achieve the main objectives in the tourism sector
18.	Dwian Hartomi Akta Padma Eldo & Azra Prabowo (2020)	Management of Funding mangrove tourism objects to become regional income by implementing POAC management	The implementation of POAC management in the tourism sector to become an income that will advance the economy
19.	Chevy Saifu Safitri (2021)	POAC management is the basic foundation for budget management of the tourism destination attraction program	Budget management uses aspects of POAC management to increase attractiveness in the tourism sector

Discussion

The Influence of the Tourism Sector on Post-Pandemic Economic Recovery

According to (Saputra and Ali, 2022) POAC's management strategy has a positive influence because it can provide a reference in carrying out economic recovery during the pandemic. (SM. Indrawati, 2021) said that Indonesia's economic growth in the second quarter of 2021 had managed to grow positively by 7.07% and described the direction and strategy of economic recovery as correct." The data shows that in the second quarter, the direction of economic recovery has been good, the economic recovery plan is also appropriate, and it has appeared to produce an impact or result." Economic recovery can be seen in all growth engines that have begun to recover.

Household demand was around 5.9%, investment at 7.5%, trade growth at 9.4%, the construction sector growth at 4.4%, the transportation sector at 25.1%, and the food and beverage accommodation sector at 21.6%. Even during the Pandemic, the Surabaya City Government is still trying to improve the economy of its citizens. Especially to MSME business actors in the city with the nickname City of Heroes. (Jannah, 2020).

According to (Fitiyani, et.al, 2020) The Covid-19 pandemic threatens human health throughout the world. Data shows that there are 4,103,539 people in the world infected with the corona virus, in Indonesia with a total of 13,645 people and in West Nusa Tenggara Province there are 330 infected people, namely 6 Orang (1.82%) died, 93 people recovered (28.18%) and are still being treated as many as 231 people (70%). In Sumbawa Regency Last update on Saturday, 9 May 2020 at 20.44 WITA a total of 9,477 people in the PPTG category (Asymptomatic Travel Perpetrators as many as 8474 people, Asymptomatic People (OTG) as many as 493 people, People Under Monitoring (ODP) as many as 443 people and 67 people Patients Under Surveillance (PDP) (<https://corona.ntbprov.go.id/list-data>).

Currently, the government and the public are required to prepare themselves to face emergency situations and act responsively in anticipating the impact of Covid-19 on the business sector as a whole. The implementation of PSBB (Large-Scale Social Restrictions) and the implementation of Work from Home (WFH) for employees, both private and government, affect the performance of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises. (Hadi and Supardi, 2020). Therefore, this POAC management strategy has a positive influence and provides improvement and development of business continuity in an effort to recover the economy.

According to (Evi et.al, 2022) The presence of Covid-19 significantly changes the structure of life because it needs to adapt and monitor changes that occur. But in addition, efforts are needed to improve the ability to deal with changes caused by the pandemic. The economy is one of the areas of human life that is growing very fast. Since man is an economic and social being, business and man are inseparable from human nature as social beings.

In this case, POAC Management can serve as a reference in carrying out Economic Recovery and National Resilience during the Covid-19 pandemic. That Planning affects what plans will be carried out in handling Economic Recovery and National Resilience. Organizing also plays an important role in Economic Recovery and National Resilience because with organizing, the government can be more focused and quickly deal with problems that occur.

Actuating also plays a role in mobilizing all government instruments, in carrying out Economic Recovery due to the pandemic. And no less important, Controlling also plays a role in supervising and regulating the progress or development of this economic recovery.

According to (Modji, 2020) In the economic field, the crisis caused by the covid-19 pandemic has developed in such a way and caused a contraction of the global economy. Unlike previous crises, it hit not only the demand side of the economy but also the supply side of the economy. Therefore, POAC Management plays

an important role in the national economic recovery.

The Influence of the Tourism Sector on Post-Pandemic Economic Recovery

According to (Sa'adah et.al, 2022) the research conducted shows that the tourism sector has a significant influence on economic recovery with urgency involving the government and also business actors. According to (Yakub 2019) the national tourism sector has an important role in economic recovery by contributing to foreign exchange, regional income, regional development, as well as absorption of investment and labor as well as business development spread across various corners of the region, Indonesia.

According to (Sigala, 2020) the Covid-19 pandemic has had an adverse influence on economic recovery because the Covid-19 virus had an impact in early 2020 when many tourists canceled their trips. According to (Lapointe, 2020) during the pandemic hit the world, many economic losses were experienced by actors in the tourism sector, thus affecting the economy.

According to (Murapi, et.al 2022) the tourism industry has a significant influence on economic recovery, so it is necessary to immediately rescue the tourism sector affected by Covid-19, by providing assistance, subsidies to relaxing loans. According to (Sugihamretha, 2020), tourism activities have a positive effect on economic recovery because tourism activities greatly affect people's livelihoods, and open opportunities to increase income for each individual. (Sutrisno, 2021) stated that the tourism sector is at least influential in terms of economic risk. According to (Fathurrahim, 2020), the post-pandemic economy will recover quickly because it is supported by the tourism sector.

According to (Wihardiyani, 2021) the tourism sector has a positive and significant influence on economic breeding in Temanggung Regency so the government immediately holds training for tourism destination managers in the context of development by implementing a new era, in the form of digitalization, increasing innovation, and cleanliness.

The tourism sector has a positive influence on the community's economy because most of the community's income depends on the tourism sector. The Covid-19 pandemic has affected the economy of the people of East Java, because most of the community's income comes from the tourism sector, so it is necessary to make an immediate recovery with the implementation and assistance of tourism destination governance during the Covid-19 pandemic.

The Influence of the Tourism Sector on E-Commerce

According to (Saputra et.al, 2022) POAC management has a positive influence on E-Commerce in every activity so that the activities carried out run effectively and efficiently. This indicates that such activities will increase significantly. Because every activity carried out is measured using a pretest and posttest.

The pretest results for entrepreneurship training obtained a score of 41% and the posttest results obtained a value of 93% showing an increase. In the pretest results for Madaro embroidery training, a score of 43% was obtained and the posttest results obtained a value of 91% increase. In the pretest results for online product marketing training, a pretest score of 45% was obtained and the posttest results obtained a value of 92%, this showed an increase.

According to Prajatama et.al, (2022) E-Commerce has a positive influence but the planning has not been fully controlled on the sustainability of an activity.

According to (Hermawati et.al, 2021) POAC management (organizational system) has a positive influence on the sustainability of activities or businesses by using E-commerce. This means that a higher level of knowledge about POAC management it has, it will support the smooth running of the business or activity by using E-commerce.

The Influence of the Tourism Sector on E-Commerce

According to (Mulyani, 2021) the use of technology through electronics or e-commerce has a positive influence because this is a solution for entrepreneurs who develop their tourism

industry business. By utilizing e-commerce in their business operations, MSMEs will get wider market access and money to attract new customers. On the other hand, it will be easier for clients to get the necessary information online. E-commerce has an important influence on business activities in the tourism sector commonly referred to as e-tourism which is used for promotional activities and tourism transactions. According to (Ismayanti, 2010) e-tourism is a concept of using ICT to increase tourism efficiency and make tourism marketing easier.

According to Ardianti, (2016) the tourism industry through e-commerce is able to increase the number of tourist visitors because visitors know more tourist information through the internet because it is easy to use. Promotion through e-commerce can increase the number of tourism visits. Visitors know more about tourist information through digital platforms than banners, pamphlets, and other promotions because the internet is easier to use.

According to Fuady (2020), technological developments (e-commerce) can revive the tourism industry in the future because the application greatly facilitates the tourism service system. Utilization of e-commerce or mobile applications to facilitate convenience in tourism travel. According to (Lai, 2015) the use of internet-based smart applications (E-Commerce) has grown rapidly in the tourism industry. According to (Davis, 2019) in encouraging the improvement of the tourism industry, the use of information technology or E-Commerce platforms can increase the growth of the tourism industry.

The Influence of POAC Management on the Tourism Sector

According to Jusmiati and Salim (2017), The concept of governance of the tourism sector of Mata Buntu Waterfall in Wasuponda District, East Luwu Regency can be carried out based on the functions of the management function, namely planning, organizing, actuating, and controlling so that the tourism object governance process can run optimally. According to Khoerunnisa (2022), in achieving a

goal of a tourist destination, it is necessary to implement POAC management in order to create an organizational body that is responsible for managing the Jiwa Temple tourist destination and can collaborate with the local government in the Karawang area.

According to Hartomi (2020), the strategy carried out by the Brebes Regency Regional Government through the Brebes Culture and Tourism Office by carrying out the POAC management function is still not optimal or still very minimal. It is expected that the POAC management function can be carried out optimally so that the management strategy carried out for Pandansari mangrove tourism objects can run well and can increase regional income to be maximized.

According to Safitri, (2021), the management of the program to increase the attractiveness of tourism destinations in Pangandaran Regency has generally been carried out well, but there are still some shortcomings where programs and activities have not been able to be fully implemented, this is where the POAC management function is needed to facilitate internal coordination and help realize the program optimally.

Conclusion

Based on the results of previous research that has been done, it can be concluded based on the results of the Systematic Literature Review of all research that has been published. First, POAC management is concerned with the tourism sector; POAC management affects post-pandemic economic recovery; POAC management affects e-commerce; Tourism sectors affect post-pandemic economic recovery; and the Tourism sector affects e-commerce.

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Conflict of interests

No conflict of interest.

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